

Trade Associations Activities and Informal Sector Tax Compliance in South-West Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to examine the role of trade associations in enhancing tax compliance among informal sector operators in South-West Nigeria, focusing on their influence in promoting awareness, reducing financial barriers, and fostering trust to improve overall compliance rates. The research employed a descriptive survey design. The population consisted of informal business operators aged 18–64 years in Nigeria's South-West region, specifically Lagos and Ogun states, selected due to their vibrant informal economies. The study utilized a purposive sampling technique to select a sample size of 180 participants. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire. The validity of the instrument was established through expert reviews, and reliability was confirmed with a Cronbach's Alpha exceeding 0.7. Data analysis employed descriptive statistics and multiple regression using SPSS. The results shows that tax awareness and education strongly influence compliance, accounting for 13.5% of the variance ($R^2 = 0.135$; $\beta = 0.367$, $p < 0.000$), with 49.4% of respondents strongly agreeing to a clear understanding of their obligations (mean = 3.14). Financial constraints are a notable barrier, explaining 3.0% of the variance ($R^2 = 0.030$; $\beta = 0.173$, $p < 0.020$), with 50.6% strongly agreeing that financial challenges hinder compliance (mean = 3.11). Trust in trade association executives positively influences compliance, contributing 4.6% of the variance ($R^2 = 0.046$; $\beta = 0.215$, $p < 0.004$), as 48.9% strongly agreed they represent members' interests effectively (mean = 3.12). The findings highlight the significant influence of tax awareness, financial constraints, trust in trade associations, and government trust on tax compliance in the informal sector. The conclusion emphasizes that improving tax education, alleviating financial barriers, and strengthening trust in both trade associations and the government are essential for enhancing tax compliance in this sector. It is recommended to focus on accessible tax education, financial support, and transparency to foster greater compliance.

Keywords: Tax awareness and education, Financial constraints, Trust in trade associations, Government trust, Tax system complexity, Tax compliance, Informal sector.

Count: 300

Introduction

Tax compliance in the informal sector is a critical challenge for governments in developing countries, where this sector significantly contributes to the economy. Taxation is a vital tool for economic growth and sustainable development, providing fiscal resources for infrastructure, social services, and governance. The informal sector, employing over 60% of the global workforce, leads to revenue losses, regulatory complexities, and economic distortions due to low tax compliance (Umar-Dauda, & Oyedokun, 2018; Adekoya et al., 2019). In Nigeria, the informal sector accounts for over 60% of GDP but contributes to a low tax-to-GDP ratio of 6%, driven by low tax morale, evasion, limited enforcement, and a complex federal structure (Oyedokun, Fowokan, Akintoye, & Dada, 2018; Adekoya et al., 2020; Rogan, 2022).

Despite initiatives like VAIDS, Nigeria struggles with taxing the informal sector, which is characterized by unregistered, cash-based enterprises with poor documentation. These businesses, often small-scale and family-owned, rely on local resources and outdated technologies, complicating tax collection (Oloyede, Kupoluyi, Oyedokun, & Benjamin, 2017; Etim & Daramola, 2020). The sector's dominance in agriculture, trade, and services (91.85% and 55.7% of respective GDP sectors) underscores its economic importance and the need for effective taxation strategies (National Bureau of Statistics, 2016; Mlanga, & Oyedokun, 2018).

Taxing the informal sector yields significant benefits for developing economies, driving increased government revenue, fostering economic growth through formalization, and strengthening governance by enhancing socio-economic engagement (Ajose, & Oyedokun, 2018; Adekoya et al., 2020). Central to this process is tax morale, the intrinsic motivation that encourages voluntary compliance among taxpayers (Feld & Frey, 2002; Oyedokun, Akintoye, & Salawu, 2018). Yet, achieving compliance remains fraught with challenges, including limited fiscal capacity, overly complex tax systems, and pervasive distrust in government institutions, all of which obstruct progress in harnessing the informal sector's potential (Babalola, Oyedokun, & Adeyemo, 2019; Sebele-Mpofu, 2020).

Several key factors shape tax compliance within the informal sector. The perceived ease of tax compliance plays a pivotal role, as simplified tax regimes and accessible processes encourage participation by reducing the burden on informal businesses (Oyedokun, Fowokan, Akintoye, & Hassan, 2018; Hammond et al., 2023). Equally important is the perceived fairness of the tax system, where equitable tax burdens and transparent, just procedures foster greater voluntary compliance among taxpayers (Olaniyi, Ajayi, & Oyedokun, 2018; Osemeke et al., 2020). Additionally, the timeliness of tax payments serves as a critical indicator of compliance, influenced by factors such as cash flow availability, awareness of deadlines, and the accessibility of payment systems (Feld & Frey, 2002; Taiwo, & Oyedokun, 2022). Together, these elements highlight the interplay of practical and perceptual dynamics in driving effective tax compliance in the informal sector.

Trade associations play a pivotal role in bridging the gap between informal businesses and tax authorities. They provide tax education, advocate for policy reforms, and facilitate financial access, addressing knowledge gaps and financial constraints (Musimenta, 2020; Oyedokun & Ayinde, 2023). Trust in association leadership and government is critical for effective compliance initiatives (Omeihe et al., 2020; Onigbinde, & Oyedokun, 2023). However, their impact on informal sector tax compliance, particularly in South-West Nigeria, remains underexplored.

Statement of the Problem

Nigeria's informal sector, driving ~70% of economic activity, faces significant tax compliance challenges due to its small-scale, cash-based nature, inadequate record-keeping, and limited resources. Trade associations offer a potential solution by bridging the gap between informal traders and the government through tax education, advocacy, and financial support. However, their effectiveness is hindered by financial constraints, complex tax systems, low tax literacy, and distrust in both association leadership and government (Dunmade et al., 2020; Musimenta, 2020; Bani-Khalid et al., 2022; Oyedokun & Sorinmade, 2023).

Key barriers include lack of tax knowledge, financial limitations, complex tax systems, and skepticism about government fairness. Trade associations could address these by simplifying tax processes, providing education, and fostering trust, yet their impact in South-West Nigeria remains underexplored. This study investigates how trade associations can enhance tax compliance in the informal sector, focusing on their intermediary role and addressing literature gaps.

Objective of the Study

This study will investigate the role of trade associations in promoting informal sector tax compliance among their members in South-West, Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study are to:

1. evaluate how effective tax awareness and education among informal sector participants influence informal sector tax compliance in South-West, Nigeria.
2. identify the financial constraints faced by informal sector participants that impact their ability to comply with tax obligations in South-West, Nigeria.
3. analyze the level of trust that members have in trade association executives and how this trust affects tax compliance efforts in South-West, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions that this study intend to address are:

1. How does the level of tax awareness and education among informal sector participants influence their tax compliance?
2. What financial constraints are faced by informal sector participants, and how do these constraints impact their ability to comply with tax obligations?
3. How does the level of trust that members have in trade association executives affect tax compliance efforts?

Hypotheses

This study will examine the following hypotheses:

H₀₁: There is no significant influence of effective tax awareness and education on informal sector tax compliance in South-West, Nigeria.

H₀₂: Financial constraints have no significant influence on informal sector tax compliance in South-West, Nigeria.

H₀₃: There is no significant influence of trust in trade association executives on informal sector tax compliance in South-West, Nigeria.

Literature Review

This chapter reviews the literature on trade associations and informal sector taxation in South-West Nigeria, organized into conceptual review, theoretical review, empirical review, conceptual links, and a summary of literature gaps.

Conceptual Review

Tax Compliance

Tax is universally defined as a mandatory payment to the government, but its interpretation varies: governments see it as revenue, businesses as an expense, and individuals as an income reduction. Nigeria's updated National Tax Policy defines tax as a legally mandated payment without direct benefits, characterized by obligation, legal backing, and no direct reciprocity (Federal Ministry of Finance, 2017; Oyedokun & Onigbinde, 2024). This emphasizes that tax payment is a compulsory, enforceable contribution, not a voluntary act.

Trade Associations

Trade associations, or industry/business associations, are organizations formed and funded by businesses within a specific sector to represent their collective interests. They advocate for favorable legislation and regulations, influencing policy to benefit their members (Aina, Aderibigbe, Adigun, & Oyedokun, 2017; Bani-Khalid et al., 2022). Additionally, they establish industry standards and best practices, often through certification programs, ensuring quality, consistency, and compliance, which enhances member credibility and competitiveness, particularly in sectors prioritizing safety and quality (Aderibigbe, Oke, & Oyedokun, 2017; Ogembo, 2019).

Theoretical Review

Institutional Theory

Institutional Theory explains how formal and informal institutions shape organizational behavior and decision-making. Originating from Max Weber's work and advanced in the 1970s by scholars like Meyer, Rowan, DiMaggio, and Powell, it posits that organizations conform to social norms for legitimacy, beyond mere efficiency (Peters, 2022). Operating within regulatory, normative, and cognitive environments, organizations become similar through isomorphism: coercive (regulatory mandates), mimetic (imitation under uncertainty), and normative (professional standards) pressures (Fowokan, Oyedokun, & Abdul, 2018; Risi et al., 2023).

In the informal sector, trade associations foster tax compliance by leveraging these pressures. Coercive isomorphism arises from legal requirements, normative from professional expectations, and mimetic from peer influence (Robertson et al., 2021). Compliance enhances legitimacy, reputation, and trust, with trade associations acting as intermediaries through education and incentives (Batrancea et al., 2022). Over time, compliance can become institutionalized, though decoupling superficial compliance remains a challenge, which trade associations address through monitoring and support (Aksom & Tymchenko, 2020). In Nigeria's context, weak regulatory enforcement and government distrust amplify trade associations' role in promoting compliance through advocacy, training, and negotiations, institutionalizing tax norms despite economic constraints (Bani-Khalid et al., 2022). While criticized for overemphasizing conformity, Institutional Theory effectively frames how external pressures shape tax compliance in the informal sector (Aksom & Tymchenko, 2020).

Conceptual Framework

Figure 2.1: Conceptual links between trade associations and informal sector taxation

Source: Researcher’s conceptualization

Methodology

This section outlines the methodological procedures used in the study, covering the research design, population, sampling techniques, instrument development, and data analysis methods. A descriptive survey design was adopted to examine relationships among variables without manipulating them. This approach allowed for the collection of quantitative data to evaluate interactions between independent and dependent variables, and to generalize findings to the broader population. The study focused on informal business operators in South-West Nigeria, specifically those aged 18–64 with at least one year of operational experience. This region, encompassing Lagos and Ogun states, is a key economic hub with a concentration of informal enterprises such as trading and craftsmanship. These businesses often operate outside formal financial systems and play a vital role in employment and economic sustainability. A purposive sampling method was used to select 180 informal business operators from Lagos and Ogun states. Questionnaires were distributed through trade association executives to participants meeting the inclusion criteria. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire divided into sections: Section A: Demographic characteristics (e.g., gender, age, marital status, years in operation, and trade group membership). Section B: Items measuring variables related to trade associations and tax compliance, using a 4-point Likert scale: Strongly Agree (4), Agree (3), Disagree (2), Strongly

Disagree (1) Cronbach's Alpha was used to assess internal consistency. A pilot test was conducted with 15% of the target population (excluded from the main study). Reliability coefficients were calculated for the five main constructs, with values ≥ 0.7 deemed acceptable. Data were collected both physically and online, with assistance from trade association representatives. Questionnaires captured respondents' perceptions on tax compliance using the Likert scale. An appendix provides a sample of the instrument.

Method of Data Analysis Both descriptive and inferential statistics were used. SPSS version 27 facilitated: Descriptive analysis of demographic variables, Pearson's correlation to assess relationships, Multiple Regression Analysis to estimate model parameters and test hypotheses. Multiple regression was used to quantify the impact of independent variables on ISTC. The general form:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \dots + \beta_n X_n + \varepsilon$$

- β_0 : Intercept
- $\beta_1 \dots \beta_n$: Coefficients
- $X_1 \dots X_n$: Independent variables
- ε : Error term

Each coefficient reflects the effect of a one-unit change in the predictor on the dependent variable, holding others constant.

Model Specification

The study adapted existing models to evaluate the influence of trade association advocacy on informal sector tax compliance. The model is stated functionally as:

$$\text{ISTC} = f(\text{TAE}, \text{FC}, \text{TTAE})$$

Where:

- **ISTC** = Informal Sector Tax Compliance
- **TAE** = Tax Awareness and Education
- **FC** = Financial Constraint
- **CTV** = Control Variables (gender, age, marital status, years in business, trade association membership)

Variable definitions:

- **Y** = ISTC (Informal Sector Tax Compliance)

- y_1 = Perceived Ease of Tax Compliance (PETC)
- y_2 = Perceived Fairness of Tax System (PFTS)
- y_3 = Timeliness of Tax Payments (TTP)

The full empirical model includes a stochastic error term to account for unexplained variance:

$$ISTC_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 TAE_i + \beta_2 FC_i + \beta_3 TTAE_i + \beta_4 GT_i + \beta_5 GEN_i + \beta_6 AGE_i + \beta_7 MS_i + \beta_8 YB_i + \beta_9 MTA_i + \varepsilon_i$$

Model Breakdown by Hypotheses

Model 1:

$$ISTC = \beta_0 + \beta_1 TAE + \varepsilon$$

(PETC, PFTS, and TTP also regressed on TAE)

Model 2:

$$ISTC = \beta_0 + \beta_1 FC + \varepsilon$$

(and for PETC, PFTS, TTP)

Model 3:

$$ISTC = \beta_0 + \beta_1 TTAE + \varepsilon$$

(and for PETC, PFTS, TTP)

Results and Discussion of Findings

This chapter presents the results and discussion of the findings from the investigation. The findings are aligned with the research questions and hypotheses formulated to address the study objectives.

Presentation of Demographic Data

Table 1: Demographic Profile of Students

Demographic Profile	Category	Frequency	Percent (%)
Age	18-24	13	7.2%
	25-34	44	24.4%
	35-44	54	30.0%
	45-54	27	15.0%
	55-64	42	23.3%
Gender	Male	124	68.9%

Year in Business	Female	56	31.1%
	1-3 Years	7	3.9%
	4-6 Years	25	13.9%
	7-10years	71	39.4%
	More than 10 years	77	42.8%
Marital Status	Married	93	51.7%
	Single	63	35.0%
	Divorced	24	13.3%
	Widow	0	0.0%
Employment status	Employed Full-time	112	62.2%
	Employed part-time	40	22.2%
	Self-employed	28	15.6%
Membership in Trade Association	Yes	105	58.3%
	No	75	41.7%

Information sector taxation

To what extent do you accurately report your business income to tax authorities?	Never accurately report	3	1.7%
	Rarely accurately report	13	7.2%
	Occasionally accurately report	18	10.0%
	Often accurately report	59	32.8%
	Always accurately report	87	48.3%
How frequently do you meet tax filing deadlines for your business	Never meet deadlines	30	16.7%
	Rarely meet deadlines	11	6.1%
	Occasionally meet deadlines	12	6.7%
	Often meet deadlines	56	31.1%
	Always meet deadlines	71	39.4%
How willing are you to participate in tax education programs provided by trade associations	Very unwilling to participate	4	2.2%
	Unwilling to participate	14	7.8%
	Neutral	27	15.0%
	Willing to participate	79	43.9%
	Very willing to participate	56	31.1%

The study participants include 180 informal business operators within the South-West., Nigeria. 180 questionnaires were administered among the respondents. Personal data of the respondents were analyzed using frequency count and percentage. Concerning gender distributions, male informal business operators are 124 representing 68.9% and female informal business operators are 56 representing 31.1%. Regarding age distribution, the largest proportion of respondents falls within the 35-44 age group, representing 30% (54) of the sample. This is followed by 25-34 age group, representing 24.4% (44) of the sample, by 55-64 age group, representing 23.3% (42) of the sample, by 45-54 age group, representing 15.0% (27) of the sample, and by 18-24 age group, representing 7.2% (13) of the sample. Analyzing years in business experience revealed that individuals with more than 10 years of business experience form the largest group at 42.8% (77). This is followed by respondents with 7-10 years of business experience, accounting for 39.4% (71) of the sample, followed by respondents with 4-6 years of business experience, accounting for 13.9% (25) of the sample, and by respondents with 1-3 years of business experience, accounting for 3.9% (7) of the sample. Regarding marital status of the informal business operators, 51.7% (93) of the respondents are married, 35.0% (63) of the respondents are single and 13.3% (24) of respondents are divorced. In terms of employment status of the operators, 112 respondents representing 62.2% are full time employed, 40 respondents representing 22.2% are part time employed and 28 respondents representing 15.6% are self-employed. When considering Membership in Trade Association, the data show that the majority of respondents (105) representing 58.3% are member of trade association while (75) representing 41.7 of sample are not member of trade association. The detail is in table 4.1.

Regarding Information sector taxation, 87 representing (48.3%) and 59 representing (32.8%) of respondent agreed that they always accurately report and often accurately report respectively report their business income to tax authorities. 71 representing (39.4%) and 56 representing (31.1%) of respondent agreed that they Always meet deadlines and Often meet deadlines respectively tax for their business. And, 56 representing (31.1%) and 79 representing (43.9%) of respondent agreed that they very willing to participate and willing to participate respectively in tax education programs provided by trade associations. The detail is in table 1.

Analysis of Research Questions

The following research questions are raised to guide the study:

Research question 1: How does the level of tax awareness and education among informal sector participants influence their tax compliance?

Table 2: Influence of Tax Awareness and Education on the Informal Sector Tax Compliance

Variable Items	Strongly								Mean
	Disagree		Disagree		Agree		Strongly Agree		
	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	
1. Tax obligations are understood by informal sector operators.	20	11.1	23	12.8	48	26.7	89	49.4	3.14
2. Trade associations offer sufficient information regarding tax compliance.	0	0.0	33	18.3	62	34.4	85	47.2	3.29
3. Paying taxes is considered essential for community development.	15	8.3	30	16.7	54	30.0	81	45.0	3.12
4. Confidence in knowledge of tax compliance regulations is present.	2	1.1	54	30.0	47	26.1	77	42.8	3.11
5. Regular attendance at tax awareness programs organized by trade associations is maintained.	12	6.7	29	16.1	66	36.7	73	40.6	3.11
Weighted Mean									3.15

Table 4.2 provides insights into respondent perceptions regarding the influence of tax awareness and education on the informal sector tax compliance. The data reveals a generally positive outlook on the influence of tax awareness and education on the informal sector tax compliance. Specifically, 49.4% of respondents strongly agreed and 26.7% of respondents agreed that tax obligations are understood by informal sector operators with mean rating ($\bar{x} = 3.14$), 47.2% of respondents strongly agreed and 34.4% of respondents agreed that trade associations offer sufficient information regarding tax compliance with mean rating ($\bar{x} = 3.29$). 45.0% of respondents strongly agreed and 30.0% of respondents agreed that paying taxes is considered essential for

community development with ($\bar{x} = 3.12$). 42.8% of respondents strongly agreed and 26.1% of respondents agreed that confidence in knowledge of tax compliance regulations is present with mean rating ($\bar{x} = 3.11$). Similarly, 40.6% of respondents strongly agreed and 36.7% of respondents agreed that regular attendance at tax awareness programs organized by trade associations is maintained with mean rating ($\bar{x} = 3.11$). The weighted mean score of the influence of tax awareness and education on the informal sector tax compliance is 3.15 ($\bar{x} = 3.15$). The weighted mean score suggested that the tax awareness and education have influence on informal sector tax compliance.

Research Question 2: What financial constraints are faced by informal sector participants, and how do these constraints impact their ability to comply with tax obligations?

Table 3: Influence of Financial Constraints on the Informal Sector Tax Compliance

Variable Item	Strongly Disagree		Disagree		Agree		Strongly Agree		Mean
	Count	%	Count	%	Count	%	Count	%	
1. Financial constraints make it difficult for me to pay taxes.	17	9.4	37	20.6	35	19.4	91	50.6	3.11
2. Trade associations help in providing financial support to meet tax obligations.	0	0.0	38	21.1	66	36.7	76	42.2	3.21
3. Access to credit or financial assistance would improve my tax compliance.	7	3.9	56	31.1	44	24.4	73	40.6	3.02
4. Trade associations help in prioritizing other financial obligations over paying taxes.	2	1.1	58	32.2	38	21.1	82	45.6	3.11
Weighted Mean									3.11

Table 3 provides insights into respondent perceptions regarding the influence of financial constraints on the informal sector tax compliance. The data reveals a generally positive outlook on the influence of financial constraints on the informal sector tax compliance. Specifically, 50.6% of respondents strongly agreed and 19.4% of respondents agreed that financial constraints make it difficult for me to pay taxes with mean rating ($\bar{x} = 3.11$), 42.2% of respondents strongly agreed

and 36.7% of respondents agreed that trade associations help in providing financial support to meet tax obligations with mean rating ($\bar{x} = 3.21$). 40.6% of respondents strongly agreed and 24.4% of respondents agreed that access to credit or financial assistance would improve my tax compliance with mean rating ($\bar{x} = 3.02$). Similarly, 45.6% of respondents strongly agreed and 21.1% of respondents agreed that trade associations help in prioritizing other financial obligations over paying taxes with mean rating ($\bar{x} = 3.11$). The weighted mean score of the influence of financial constraints on the informal sector tax compliance is 3.11 ($\bar{x} = 3.11$). The weighted mean score suggested that the financial constraints have influence on informal sector tax compliance.

Research Question 3: How does the level of trust that members have in trade association executives affect tax compliance efforts?

Table 4: Influence of Trust on Trade Association Executives on the Informal Sector Tax Compliance

Variable Item	Strongly Disagree		Disagree		Agree		Strongly Agree		Mean
	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	
	1. Trust in trade association executives to effectively represent interests is present.	12	6.7	40	22.2	40	22.2	88	
2. Trust in trade association leadership impacts willingness to comply with tax regulations.	0	0.0	42	23.3	60	33.3	78	43.3	3.20
3. Trade association executives are transparent regarding the use of collected fees and resources.	7	3.9	57	31.7	43	23.9	73	40.6	3.01
4. Concerns or suggestions about tax compliance have been raised with trade association executives.	3	1.7	55	30.6	36	20.0	86	47.8	3.14
Weighted Mean									3.12

Table 4 provides insights into respondent perceptions regarding the influence of trust in trade association executives on the informal sector tax compliance. The data reveals a generally positive

outlook on the influence of trust in trade association executives on the informal sector tax compliance. Specifically, 48.9% of respondents strongly agreed and 22.2% of respondents agreed that Trust in trade association executives to effectively represent interests is present with mean rating ($\bar{x} = 3.13$), 43.3% of respondents strongly agreed and 33.3% of respondents agreed that Trust in trade association leadership impacts willingness to comply with tax regulations with mean rating ($\bar{x} = 3.20$). 40.6% of respondents strongly agreed and 23.9% of respondents agreed that trade association executives are transparent regarding the use of collected fees and resources with mean rating ($\bar{x} = 3.02$). Similarly, 47.8% of respondents strongly agreed and 20.0% of respondents agreed that concerns or suggestions about tax compliance have been raised with trade association executives with mean rating ($\bar{x} = 3.14$). The weighted mean score of the influence of trust in trade association executives on the informal sector tax compliance is 3.12 ($\bar{x} = 3.12$). The weighted mean score suggested that the trust in trade association executives have influence on informal sector tax compliance.

Discussion of Findings

The study upheld that tax awareness and education have a statistically significant positive influence on informal sector tax compliance in South-West Nigeria. This finding aligns with previous studies. Specifically, Oloyede and Nwachukwu (2021) found that educating the public about taxation, promoting inter-agency collaboration, issuing Tax Identification Numbers (TINs), and ensuring government transparency were essential to fostering compliance in the informal sector. Similarly, Joshi, Prichard, and Heady (2014) argued that imposing taxes on the informal sector can increase revenue collection and positively impact a nation's economic development.

Conclusion

The findings show that tax awareness and education, financial constraints, trust in trade association executives, and government trust all significantly influence tax compliance in the informal sector. Tax awareness and education were positively linked to compliance, with respondents indicating a strong understanding of their obligations. Financial constraints were recognized as a barrier, but access to financial support could improve compliance. Trust in trade associations and government transparency were also important factors in encouraging compliance. However, the complexity of

the tax system was not viewed as a major obstacle. Thus, enhancing tax awareness, reducing financial barriers, and building trust in both trade associations and the government are essential for improving tax compliance in the informal sector.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, several recommendations were made to improve tax compliance in the informal sector.

First, the findings emphasize the importance of tax awareness and education in encouraging tax compliance. It is recommended that government bodies and trade associations enhance their efforts in providing accessible and comprehensive tax education programs to informal sector operators. These programs should focus on clarifying tax obligations, benefits of compliance, and available resources for assistance. Increased awareness through workshops, seminars, and easily digestible online content could empower informal sector workers to better understand their tax responsibilities and improve overall compliance rates.

Second, while financial constraints were identified as a barrier to tax payment, there is an opportunity to support informal sector operators. It is recommended that trade associations and financial institutions collaborate to provide tailored financial products and services, such as microloans or tax relief programs, specifically designed for informal sector businesses. This could ease the financial burden on operators and enable them to meet their tax obligations. Additionally, governments should explore the possibility of offering tax incentives or subsidies for informal sector operators who demonstrate consistent tax compliance.

Third, trust in trade association executives was found to positively influence tax compliance. To further build on this trust, trade associations should prioritize transparency in their operations, especially regarding the use of collected fees and resources. Regular communication with members about how their contributions are being utilized will foster a stronger sense of accountability and encourage greater willingness to comply with tax regulations. Trade associations should also work on strengthening their advocacy efforts, ensuring that their leadership effectively represents the interests of informal sector operators.

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